

1. OPTIMISATION OF LAYER AND FIBRE ADHESION IN DRY FIBRE PLACEMENT PROCESSES FOR SNOWBOARD PREFORM

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ABSTRACT

Dry fibre placement (DFP) has great potential to save material and improve the mechanical properties of carbon preforms due to lower undulation compared to woven fabrics. The aim of this work is to optimise the layer and fibre adhesion in dry fibre placement processes, in particular on a new dry fibre placement machine (NNS = near net shape). The layer and fibre adhesion is important for the further processing and transport of the preforms. For this purpose, four different powder binders with different proportions and a veil are tested. The powder is applied to the carbon roving with the aid of a spreader. The amount of binder applied is being varied by the speed of the spreader. Although a larger amount of binder improves handling, it also reduces the mechanical properties of the final composite. It is therefore important to find the optimum proportion for each binder. The preforms are evaluated with regard to their handling and stability during laminating process. In addition, tensile and loosening tests are carried out with test specimens. Based on these results and the evaluation of the handling, a comprehensive assessment can be made of each binder and the required binder quantities.

2. INTRODUCTION

In the dry fibre placement process, unidirectional rovings are spread and placed as tapes. The special feature of the NNS system used here compared to conventional DFP systems is a 360° rotating placement table. The advantages of this process are optimum fibre alignment and placement, as well as the associated low waste rate. Load introduction and functional elements can be integrated directly [1]. In addition, the fibres can also be laid directly in line with the load path [2]. Another advantage is the high flexibility of the process. The grammage of the preform can be specifically adjusted by spreading the fibres. At the same time, the spreaded rovings have low fibre crimp and fibre undulation [3]. The DFP process can also be combined with other fibre placement processes, such as Tailored Fibre Placement (TFP). [4, 5]

To stabilise the fabric for further processing, a binder is applied during the process. The thermosetting and/or thermoplastic binder can be applied in the form of a fleece/veil, as a powder or as a liquid system. In the next process step, the binder is activated by pressure and heat. [6] The aim of the following tests is to determine the optimum binder content. On the one hand, too little binder is reflected in poor handling. On the other hand, the binder closes

potential flow channels for the resin. It therefore has a significant influence on the permeability and the impregnability of the preform. The permeability of DFP preforms is 1-2 times lower than the permeability of conventional textile surfaces (woven fabrics or non-crimp fabrics). [7, 8] As the binder has a significant influence on the adhesive properties of the tapes, it also affects the drapability of the preform. [9] A chemical reaction with the resin system applied later is also possible and could lead to lower mechanical properties.

Four powder binders and a thermoplastic veil are tested for this work. In the NNS-system used, the powder binders are fed to a porous spreader roller via a hopper. The veil is placed on top of the respective preform layer. After the depositing process, tensile samples are cut out of the preforms. During this process, the handling of the preforms is assessed in terms of stability during cutting and transport. The results are then used to elaborate a specific guidance for each binder.

In terms of lightweight construction, the future of sports equipment also lies in the use of carbon fibres. This is also the case for snowboards and their subgroup, splitboards. Instead of the usual use of sandwich structures and fibre-reinforced plastics, carbon preforms are to be used here too. By depositing rovings in the correct load path, not only can the properties of the end product be specifically customised, but also the shape and size. With the help of the DFP process, for example, the waste rate for carbon can be reduced by approx. 74% in the production of a splitboard (compared to semi-finished fibre products with a standardised width). Depending on the material used, the pure material costs are thus reduced by 71 - 84 %. [10, 11] The connection between the components is important for the durability of the splitboard. The interaction of snowboard components, fibres, binder and resin system is fundamental here.

When using carbon fibres, the high CO₂-footprint during production is to taking into concerns. When manufacturing a snowboard, carbon fibres achieve the best values in terms of technical performance compared to glass fibres and flax. In terms of environmental criteria, however, carbon fibres are far behind the two other options they should therefore be used strategically. [12]

3. RESEARCH TESTS & EXPERIMENTS

A four-layer rectangular preform with a fibre orientation of $\pm 45^\circ$ is produced for the test. The binders used are referred by their abbreviated designations. The designations are 602, 603, TRAC (all three from Epikote™) and Silb. In the tests, only the speed of the spreader and thus the amount of binder applied is varied. All other settings remain unchanged. A preform without binder is produced as a reference. All preforms are weighed after finishing. The binder content is then calculated from the difference to the reference preform. It is also possible to detect the amount of binder on the roving with a camera system. [8]

3 - 4 spreader settings are used for each powder binder. As the binders have different particle sizes, the spreader settings are not transferable. That means different binder quantities are to

be expected. According to former research the binder content should not exceed 5%. While the powder binders are applied during the process, the veil must be applied manually. The layering is carried out once after each layer of the carbon preform (sample designation GV) and once after every second layer (GGV).

The handling of the samples was determined subjectively by evaluating the fibre displacements and the potentially loosened tapes. The tensile samples are cut out of the centre of the preform using a rolling knife. The resistance to shear forces is assessed. In addition, the fibre, tape and layer displacement is also considered and tested by moving the samples with a defined speed. As the preform always has to be moved away from the placement table, handling without fibre displacement is extremely important for error-free further processing.

In order to validate the preliminary subjective assessment of the handling, tensile tests are carried out in accordance to DIN EN ISO 527-2. The clamping length of the samples is 150 mm, the clamping pressure 1 bar, the preload 1 N and the test speed 20 mm/min. A delamination point is to be expected during the tensile tests. This corresponds to the load that must not be exceeded during further processing, e.g. during lamination or transport.

4. RESULTS

The test results for handling and tensile tests are listed in Table 1. However, the table only contains the analysable results.

Table 1: Summary of the test results

Sample	Spreader setting	Binder content [%]	Handling Cutting Displacement	F _{max} [N]	F _{maxA} [N]	σ _m [MPa]	σ _{mA} [MPa]
603 I	5	1.59	- -	7.40	2.38	0.21	0.07
603 II	60	2.87	+ ±	13.64	6.06	0.39	0.17
603 III	30	1.85	± -	4.68	3.06	0.12	0.09
603 IV	80	4.34	+ +	19.38	11.66	0.55	0.33
Silb I	30	2.99	+ ±	7.73	4.43	0.22	0.13
Silb II	20	2.54	+ ±	4.92	2.34	0.14	0.07
Silb III	0	2.44	+ ±	3.19	2.26	0.09	0.06
Silb IV	50	3.60	+ ±	7.85	4.82	0.22	0.14
TRAC III	70	5.60	+ +	24.88	16.87	0.71	0.48
GV	-	4.80	+ ±	273.98	16.60	7.83	0.47

Legend: poor (-); average (±); good (+)

Some tests did not achieve the pre-tensioning force (preload) of the tensile tests due to their poor handling and therefore a poor fibre and layer connection. Consequently, these tests can be categorised as unsuitable for further processing. For this reason, the complete test series 602 is not listed. Here, even with a spreader setting of 70 and a binder content of 3.23 %, an unsatisfactory result is achieved. As very good results are achieved with other binders and a

similar binder content, it can be assumed that this binder is unsuitable for the materials and settings used. Two further tests are also carried out with the TRAC binder. Binder proportions of 2.62 % and 3.26 % are applied here. The handling of these preforms is assessed as unacceptable. It was not possible to bond the tapes across layers. The preforms are not suitable for further processing. In the third test, acceptable handling was achieved with a binder content of 5.60 %.

The particle size of the powder determines how much binder can be transported in the pores of the spreader. With larger grains, more binder is applied per particle. Consequently, the proportion of binder is correspondingly higher at the same spreading speed. These differences with the same setting can be seen between test series 603 and Silb in Table 1.

Test series 603 shows an almost linear progression. Handling improves with increasing binder content. Perfect handling is finally achieved with a binder content of 4.34 %. Here both, cutting and displacement (fibre, tape, and layer adhesion) are rated as very good. Figure 1 shows the stress-strain curve of the tensile tests. A first peak can be recognized here at an elongation of approx. 0.7 %. At this point, the sample begins to delaminate. There is a transition from the elastic to the plastic range. The preform is therefore unusable for an application (lamination etc.). The elastic area is defined below as the application area. The delamination of the fabric parts can be seen in Figure 3. The associated values for the application area (tensile force $F_{\max A}$, tension σ_{mA}) can be found in Table 1. The maximum tensile force in the application area increases with increasing binder content and finally reaches 11.66 N in test 603 IV. The high amount of binder causes the rovings to bond across fibres, layers and tapes. There is no displacement possible. As a result, the tensile specimen shows a significantly more elastic deformation. No drop in the increase after delamination can be recognised in the stress-strain curve.

Figure 1: Stress-strain diagram of test series 603 including assessment of handling

An unusual behavior occurs when viewing the Silb test series. Saturation occurs as the binder content increases. Between the settings 30 and 50, i.e. the binder proportions 2.99 % and 3.60 %, there is no significant increase in the handling or the stress-strain values. This

correlation can be seen in Figure 2. Paradoxically, good handling is achieved even at the lowest spreader setting despite the low strain coefficients. This indicates a very good bond between roving and binder. The melting range is optimally utilized. The resistance to shear forces (handling) is obviously greater than that to tensile forces. The low elongation coefficients play a subordinate role in the subsequent laminate anyway, as the forces are mainly absorbed by the matrix, the resin. For a usable preform a binder content of 2.44 % is already sufficient for the area of application. A higher binder content would only have a negative effect on the fibre volume content and permeability.

Figure 2: Stress-strain curve of the test series Silb

The Veil differs from the previously analysed powder composites both in terms of application and characteristics. It is available in a thin textile form, as a fleece. Due to the connection via the individual fibres of the fleece, larger areas can be connected in the surface. This is advantageous for handling during transport and cutting, as well as for handling during subsequent lamination. The two-dimensional bonding prevents fibrewash. However, it is not possible to set exact binder proportions with the Veil. By specifying the grammage, the binder content can only be controlled gradually, with application between every layer or every second (third,...) layer.

The preform laid down for these tests has no gaps between the tapes due to its laying file or the settings on the NNS system. As the rovings are spread and the layers are also placed with an offset of 15 mm, any gaps are closed. For this reason, no cross-layer connection is achieved by applying the veil after two preform layers (GGV). However, if the Veil is applied after each carbon layer and additionally activated by heat on the heating frame, a fixed scrim can be produced.

In order to further optimise the layer adhesion and thus the handling of the preform GV, gaps must be created at this point. An additional layer of Veil must also be applied to the underside. At this point, it should be mentioned that the Veil leaves a kind of shroud on the top of the preform (Figure 3) after melting. The appearance and surface is much better with the powder binders.

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The stress-strain values of the preform GV clearly exceed those of the powder connectors. The direct comparison can be seen in Figure 4. An average maximum tensile force of 273.9 N is achieved. With the support of the Veil, twice the change in length can be achieved in some cases. At the same time, the elongation in this test series is about 10 % higher than with the powder binders.

Figure 3: Delamination of the samples in the tensile tests

Figure 4: Force-length diagram with all tensile tests in comparison

Thanks to the closed adhesion of the fibres with the Veil, tearing of tapes is prevented. Only the first layer can tear out, as no veil was applied here. The different behaviour of the two preform sides can be seen in Figure 3. The delamination of the lowest preform layer is reflected in a decrease in the increase in the stress-strain diagram (at approx. 4 % strain). Due to this early delamination on the underside, the GV sample only reaches 6 % of the maximum value in its application range. The difference of the powder binders is small at this point, as can be seen in the lower diagram of Figure 4. TRAC III, on the other hand, achieves 68 % of the maximum value in the application range, which corresponds to 16.87 N and a stress of 0.48 MPa. This is followed by sample 603 IV. This also has relatively high stress-strain values in the application range. The other powder binders are in the same range (approx. 3 - 8 N) with regard to their behaviour up to delamination. Table 1 lists the maximum tensile force and elongation, as well as the values up to delamination. Figure 4 shows this relationship graphically once again.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Based on the specific assessment of the handling and the stress-strain characteristics, a recommendation for action can be issued. This recommendation for action represents the best possible layer and fibre adhesion for the binder type on the NNS system used.

In the case of the powder binders, Silb, TRAC and 603 proved to be suitable. With the TRAC, acceptable results are only achieved with the specified settings at a binder content of over 5 %. Due to the low cross-linking temperature, the heating power must be controlled to prevent cross-linking. Based on the findings of the other powder binders, good results are conceivable from a binder content of approx. 3 %. With Silb, on the other hand, very good handling results were achieved even with a low binder content (2.44 %). Only the elongation values are lower than those of the other tests. However, these play a minor role in the subsequent bond. The low amount of binder has a positive effect on the permeability. In test series 603, a binder content of 2.87 % proved to be sufficient. The elongation values here are comparatively good. The handling is also good and does not increase further with higher binder percentages.

The Veil already shows very high maximum values in the GV layering. In order to optimise handling in the future, VGV layering is recommended. This means that a layer of Veil must be applied before the first preform layer. In order not to neglect the impregnability of the preform, the rovings must be laid down with gaps and without offsetting the layers. At this point, however, it should not be forgotten that the application of the Veil requires additional time, as it cannot be applied during the running process like the powders. At the same time, the binder content cannot be varied with the Veil.

During the tests, the DFP process proved to be very suitable for the production of preforms; the handling is simple with very good preform results. At this point, it should be mentioned that the tests carried out here are exclusively intended to analyse handling. The effects of the different binder types and proportions on the mechanical properties are analysed separately. For this purpose, further tests such as bending tests, tensile tests in the laminate and fibre wash

tests are carried out. In addition, the compatibility with the various snowboard components (peel tests) will also be tested.

6. REFERENCES

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